
Assessing climate change risk in the municipality of Lemvig

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Synopsis:

This essay examines current and future climate-related risks for the municipality of Lemvig, with a focus on the impacts of sea-level rise, storm surges, and increased precipitation intensity. Risk maps based on projected climate scenarios are used to assess potential flooding and its implications for the harbour, urban areas, and critical infrastructure.

Beyond risk identification, the essay explores adaptation strategies under conditions of uncertainty, emphasising the need for scalable and flexible planning approaches. The discussion situates Lemvig as a case where climate change adaptation extends beyond prevention, highlighting resilience and the capacity to live with water as central components of sustainable urban development.

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Introduction

1

Climate change depends primarily on the level of greenhouse gases (GHG) in the atmosphere. These GHG are mostly produced by human activities. Four scenarios that characterize plausible climate futures and illustrate policy choices have been proposed by the most recent Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Assessment Report (AR₅) [Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2014]. These scenarios known as Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) are consistent with the wide range of scenarios available in the published literature. These future climate projections include a low GHG emission scenario (RCP2.6), two intermediate scenarios (RCP4.5 and RCP6.0) and one scenario with very high GHG emissions (RCP8.5) [Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut, 2018].

Figure 1.1. RCP Scenarios [Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut, 2018]

The first of the two intermediate scenarios, RCP_{4.5}, assumes a reduction in the GHG emissions by mid-century and a stabilization of the emissions by the end of the century. In this scenario, the increase in the global mean surface temperature is likely to be from 1.1°C to 2.6°C. On the other hand, RCP_{8.5} assumes that GHG emissions continue rising until 2100, leading to CO₂ concentrations of more than 1000 ppm. This scenario is usually called 'business as usual', and projects an increase of the global mean surface temperature from 2.6°C to 4.8°C. [Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2014].

1.1 Lemvig

Lemvig municipality is located in the north-west Jylland and it is part of Midtjylland Region, covering an area of 508,17km² [Adminstat, 2020], whereas the city itself is covering an area of 4,89 km² [Google Earth Pro, 2020]. It is located in and over a deep valley (see 1.2) with an elevation going from 1m above sea level to 27m in the western part of the city, 45m in its southern part, and 60m in its eastern part. The valley, at the south-east, has a slope with an elevation of only 3,9 meters separating the sea and the city from a natural lake (these elevations are obtained using the "elevation profile tool" of Google Earth Google Earth Pro [2020]).

Figure 1.2. Map of Lemvig [SCALGO live, 2020]

Per 2020, Lemvig has a total population of 6.895 inhabitants, while the municipality has 19.722 inhabitants [Lemvig kommune, 2020a]. The demographic composition in Lemvig is curved to the elderly side, with 45 pct. of the population being between 45 and 74 years old. Furthermore, the population decreased by 2.278 persons from 2008 to 2020 [Adminstat, 2020].

1.2 Problem: sea-level rise

Denmark is the second lowest country in the European Union (EU) [C2C, 2020]. Therefore, Danish cities are more vulnerable over rising sea levels than most countries in the EU. Sea-level rise and stronger storm surges have already caused problems in Lemvig. For example, the storms Bodil, Egon and Urd [Klimatorium, 2020a] threatened the harbour front. Based on this, there is a need for further risk assessment and climate change adaptation. In 2012, the city of Lemvig built a sea-wall, called "Le Mur" (see Figure 1.3). This 600m long concrete barrier [Lemvig kommune, 2020b], integrated with the urban landscape, is used to protect the city against sea-level rises up to 120cm [Climate change adaptation, 2020]. The construction required an investment of 18 million DKK and was designed by Hasløv & Kjærsgaard Architects and constructed by SHS-Byg [Broch, 2020].

Figure 1.3. "Le Mur", marked in red, seen from above [Ministry of the Environment and Food of Denmark / Environmental Protection Agency, 2014]

A focus point of the municipality is the attractiveness of the harbour front and thus the wall was constructed accordingly [Climate change adaptation, 2020]. As shown in Figure 1.4, it divides the area into smaller parts to create room for leisure activities and social cohesion. On the one hand, the wall aims to provide protection to the city for more extreme flood events, and on the other hand it aims to redefine a living port area, that can be used as a meeting and relaxation point for the city [Orange Beton A/s, N.Y.]. In that case, the wall can be seen as something positive rather than only a way to protect from a threat [Lemvig kommune, 2014].

Figure 1.4. "Le Mur" as a place for leisure activities. Photo: Counterframe [Broch, 2020]

However, the wall is not always enough, especially when more severe storms hit Denmark. In 2013 the water ran over the wall where the municipality had to pump the water back over the wall again. The storm Bodil rose the normal water level up above 1,83 meters. In 2015 the storm Egon hit north-western Europe, and rose the sea level in Lemvig up 1,95 meters above normal level. The storm Egon was characterised as a 100-year event [Klimatorium, 2020a].

Figure 1.5. "Le Mur", the wall in action [Lemvig Kommune, 2015]

In 2016 the storm Urd also hit Lemvig, and was accountable for a sea-level rise of about 1,77 meters above normal sea level [Klimatorium, 2020a]. The sea level will, in general, rise up to 185 cm in a 20-year incident; thus the wall is already not enough, and especially not when taking into account the 50- or the 100-year incidents [Klimaatlas, 2020]. It is not only during storm floods that Lemvig has problems, but also during heavy rain events where the sewage can not keep up and overflow and thus the water runs back up. The municipality has dimensioned the sewage up to a 5-year rain event, according to the Danish regulation [Lemvig kommune, 2014].

On a side note, to help developing the needed sustainable climate change adaptation and protecting the harbour front and the city of Lemvig, it is suitable to include various stakeholders, such as the municipality, experts, as well as citizens [Klimatorium, 2020b].

This report will therefore focus on making a risk assessment on climate change effects in Lemvig, by making an analysis of these risks, and give recommendations of possible solutions to be adopted.

While mitigation remains essential to limit long-term impacts, this report starts from the premise that a significant degree of climate change is already unavoidable.

Consequently, the focus of this assessment is not only on preventing future damage, but on understanding how Lemvig can adapt and build resilience to impacts that are already unfolding and will intensify over time.

In this sense, climate adaptation is treated not as a failure of mitigation, but as a necessary and proactive planning strategy.

Analysis 2

For this analysis, the scenarios RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 are used. The selection of these pathways is based on the following reason: The Danish Government recommends the use of these paths for planning scenarios, depending on the time horizon as well as the level of robustness [Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut, 2018].

As shown in Figure 2.1, a very high demand in robustness and a long-time planning requires the use of the RCP8.5. Considering short term planning, scenario 4.5 is recommended regardless of the level of robustness needed.

Figure 2.1. Choosing the right RCP [Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut, 2018]

Therefore, RCP4.5 data for the period 2041-2070 and RCP8.5 data for the period 2071-2100 were used to get an overall overview of possible future events and to analyse its impacts on the city of Lemvig. Additionally, the analysis showed that the scenario with RCP4.5 2071-2100 and RCP8.5 in 2041-2070 were too similar to give additional information. Data about the change in the average of sea level for 20- and 50-year daily storm surge events from Klimaatlas [Klimaatlas, 2020], as well as change in precipitation levels, were visualized using the platform SCALGO [SCALGO live, 2020]. Additionally, to calculate the area of flooded sectors, AutoCAD software was used along with Klimaatlas and SCALGO [AutoCAD, 2020].

2.1 Changes in sea level - Storm surges – 20-year event

During a 20-year storm surge event, both the harbour front (the area between the sea line and the roads Strandvejen, Havnegade and Teglgårdsvej), and the inner city of Lemvig (the area between the mentioned roads and the lake) would be damaged by the sea-level rise (see Figure 2.2).

Indeed, RCP4.5 scenario, in the period 2041-2070, projects the water to reach an average of 201cm (uncertainty interval: 180-225cm). RCP8.5 (period 2071-2100), projects the average water level to be 242cm (uncertainty interval: 197-288cm) [KlimaAtlas, 2020].

However, there are major differences regarding the sea water depth in these two areas. In RCP4.5, the depth of water in the beginning of the harbour front reaches 200cm in certain points, while in the inner city the maximum depth of water is approximately 90cm. For the RCP8.5 scenario, the depth of water in the beginning of the harbour front reaches 200cm in certain points, while in the inner city the maximum depth of water is approximately 130cm [SCALGO live, 2020].

Figure 2.2. Left: RCP4.5 projection of the average sea-level rise in Lemvig for the period 2041/2070. Right: RCP8.5 projection of the average sea-level rise in Lemvig for the period 2071/2100 [SCALGO live, 2020]

Based on both RCP4.5 and 8.5 scenarios previously mentioned, it can be observed the harbour front is the most affected area by the rise of sea water along with the city's East coast. Indeed, the harbour would be completely flooded for both RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios. The East coast would be also highly affected by floods, except for some residential areas (see Figure 2.3).

In the inner city, the area surrounding the road Enghavevej (see Figure A.1), which represents a big part of the city center, is the most affected area by the sea-level rise (see Figure A.1). The water depth on this road and in most of its surroundings would be around 50cm for the RCP4.5, and around 90cm for the RCP8.5. In this area, four of the five biggest supermarkets, as well as the hospital of Lemvig, are located (see Figure A.2).

Figure 2.3. Left: RCP4.5 projection of the average sea-level rise in Lemvig for the period 2041/2070. Right: RCP8.5 projection of the average sea-level rise in Lemvig for the period 2071/2100 [SCALGO live, 2020]

Additionally, the road Enghavevej leads to the northern part of Lemvig lake (see Figure A.2). Using SCALGO, it is observed that this area will be flooded in all scenarios, which would result in sea water merging with the lake. In this area, the highest values of water depth are predicted to be approx. 120cm for RCP4.5 and approx. 160cm for RCP8.5 [SCALGO live, 2020]. However, most of this area is covered by a football field [Google Maps, 2020], thus, the magnitude of the possible damage could be less than in the City Centre.

Figure 2.4. Left: RCP4.5 projection of the average sea-level rise in Lemvig for the period 2041/2070. Right: RCP8.5 projection of the average sea-level rise in Lemvig for the period 2071/2100 [SCALGO live, 2020]

2.2 Changes in sea level - Storm surges – 50-year event

During a 50-year storm surge event, the effects of the sea-level rise are similar to the ones produced by a 20-year storm surge event. The average water level rise for RCP4.5, in the period 2041-2070, is projected to be 208cm (uncertainty interval: 186 - 235cm). For RCP8.5, in the period 2071-2100, the average sea-level rise is projected to be 249cm (uncertainty interval: 204-297cm) [Klimaatlas, 2020]. The water depth increases around 7cm in most of the harbour front [SCALGO live, 2020].

Figure 2.5. Left: RCP4.5 projection of the average sea-level rise in Lemvig for the period 2041/2070. Right: RCP8.5 projection of the average sea-level rise in Lemvig for the period 2071/2100 [SCALGO live, 2020]

The major differences are found in the inner city and the southern part of the lake. In the inner city, water spreads to the western part of the city center. The slight difference of 7cm in sea-level rise between the RCP8.5 20-year event scenario and the 50-year event scenario is the flooding of an extra 1.80 hectares. The Lemvig library and Lemvig Lutheran church, located in the city centre, are at risk along with parts of the field located next to the southern part of the lake, where the water advances 30 metres (see Figure A.1) [SCALGO live, 2020].

Therefore, the rise of the water level in Lemvig not only represents a challenge to protect the infrastructure in the affected areas, but also threatens the cultural and environmental values of Lemvig.

Figure 2.6. Left: RCP4.5 projection of the average sea-level rise in Lemvig for the period 2041/2070. Right: RCP8.5 projection of the average sea-level rise in Lemvig for the period 2071/2100 [SCALGO live, 2020]

Figure 2.7. Left: RCP4.5 projection of the average sea-level rise in Lemvig for the period 2041/2070. Right: RCP8.5 projection of the average sea-level rise in Lemvig for the period 2071/2100 [SCALGO live, 2020]

Although these events are classified as extremely unlikely in annual probability terms, the magnitude of the potential damage and the disruption to critical infrastructure render them unacceptable from a resilience and urban continuity perspective.

2.2.1 Flooded areas

Based on the maps extracted from SCALGO and contrasted surfaces calculated with a Computer-Aided Design (CAD) program, table 2.1 was constructed. The annual probability taken for a 20-year event is 5 pct. The annual probability taken for a 50-year event is 2 pct [Lemvig kommune, 2014].

In both 20- and 50-year storm surge event, there is a difference in sea-level rise of 41cm between RCP4.5 and RCP8.5. The difference of the flooded area between RCP8.5 and RCP4.5 for a 20-year event is 9.09 hectares while the difference between these scenarios for a 50-year event is 9.29 hectares.

In a 50-year event, the sea level rises 7cm more compared to a 20-year event for both RCP4.5 and RCP8.5. The difference of flooded area is 1.80 hectares more for a RCP8.5 50-year event compared to a RCP8.5 20-year event. In a RCP4.5 50-year event, the flooded area increases by 1.60 hectares compared to a RCP4.5 20-year event.

Therefore, great differences are found regarding flooded areas between scenarios RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 of 20- and 50-year events, while only minor differences are found within a single scenario between mid century and the end of the century.

Period	SCN	Type of event	Sea Rise Average (cm)	Maximum rise Sea level (cm)	Overflood Coverage Average (Ha)	Overflood Coverage Max. (ha)	Overflood City pct. (Av.)	Risk Magnitude
2041	4.5	20 yr/ev	201	225	53,78	60,25	10.99	3,01
		50 yr/ev	208	235	55,38	61,87	11.32	1,23
2070	8.5	20 yr/ev	213	241	57,06	62,67	11.67	3,13
		50 yr/ev	220	250	58,85	64,81	12.04	1,29
2071	4.5	20 yr/ev	213	248	57,06	64,56	11.67	3,22
		50 yr/ev	220	257	58,85	65,97	12.36	1,31
2100	8.5	20 yr/ev	242	288	62,87	71,53	12.86	3,57
		50 yr/ev	249	297	64,68	72,72	13.23	1,45

Table 2.1. Overflood data taken from Klimaatlas and used in SCALGO to determinate the flooded area in Lemvig. [Klimaatlas, 2020] [SCALGO live, 2020]

2.3 Precipitations - the risk of a flood from Lemvig lake

Figure 2.8. Lemvig lake [Visit Denmark, 2020]

Except for the storm and sea-level rise, another risk for Lemvig area is the stronger precipitation that will likely happen because of climate change [Lemvig kommune, 2014]. Lemvig Lake in particular is prone to overflow quickly in case of strong precipitations, as seen in the following SCALGO simulations in figure 2.9.

Figure 2.9. Overflowing Lemvig lake [SCALGO live, 2020]

As observed from this simulation, Lemvig lake can only accommodate small rain events: it starts overflowing and reaching building in its southern part from 33mm/day rain, and in its northern part from 45mm/day rain.

However, SCALGO only computes precipitation in an instantaneous way, and doesn't allow to consider the sewage systems that could accommodate for part of the precipitation. Yet it still indicates where the water would go in that case scenario, that is to say: it would overflow both in the northern and southern side of the lake.

The Denmark's legislation requires municipalities to dimension their sewage system to accommodate for a 5-year rain event [Lemvig kommune, 2014]. According to Klimaatlas [Klimaatlas, 2020], a 5-year precipitation event in Lemvig region corresponds to 60mm/day rain. Therefore, a 45mm/day rain event would actually not be a problem. However, future stronger events may not be accommodated. For the following analysis, a sewage system accommodating for a 60mm/day rain event is used. Considering the future 20-year events and 50-year events precipitation for RCP4.5 and 8.5, the precipitation level according to Klimaatlas will be:

- 80 mm/day rain for a 20-year event with RCP4.5 (for the whole period of present to 2100)
- from 90 to 100 mm/day rain for a 50-year event with RCP4.5 or a 20-year event with RCP8.5 (for the whole period of present to 2100)
- 111 mm/day rain maximum for a 50-year event with RCP8.5 for the late period of 2071-2100

This would therefore mean that the lake could effectively overflow, causing a threat to some part of the city without proper intervention. These areas at risk are the same as those previously mentioned for the 50-year event storm surge. Overall it is less likely and less risky for Lemvig to have the lake overflow from precipitations than the aforementioned issues caused by the sea-level rise and storm surges events.

2.4 Risk Analysis

To assess the different risk posed by a rise of sea level, a table of damage magnitude is proposed. This table function as a risk assessment tool to indicate what scenario poses the bigger risk. While an holistic approach should be followed to do an analysis of this nature [UNDRR, 2019], this report is limited only to the spatial impact and the possible outcomes of the water level rise and precipitation. The definition of the damage magnitude, as a percentage of flooded city, is as follows:

Damage magnitude	Flooded area of Lemvig
Catastrophic	More than 10%
Critical	5.1 - 10%
Marginal	0 - 5%

The occurrence probability is defined as the IPCC does in their fifth Assessment Report (AR5) [Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2014], using the same definitions as in the next table:

Occurrence	Probability to have the event
Extremely likely	95-100%
More likely than not	50-100%
Extremely unlikely	0-5%

Continuing with the definitions, the possible outcomes in a city without better improvements are proposed as follows:

- A red outcome implies possible major structural damages, obstructed communication routes, obstructed supply chain, major damage to buildings and equipment, merge of fresh water with sea water.
- An orange outcome implies possible structural damages, possible obstructed communications routes, possible obstructed supply chain, possible damage to buildings and equipment, merge of fresh water with sea water.
- A yellow outcome implies some structural damages, some obstructions in communications routes, some damages to buildings equipment.

These definitions should be defined with a more extensive and detailed future analysis taking in consideration other aspects such as social and cultural impacts not mentioned in this report.

Evaluating the selected scenarios into a risk matrix (2.2) generated with the previously described definitions, it is observed that all scenarios have catastrophic consequences for the city, even though all are extremely unlikely.

Flooded area of the city	Catastrophic	More than 10.1%	A-B-G-H		
	Critical	5.1-10%			
	marginal	0-5%			
			0-5%	50-100%	95-100%
			Extremely unlikely	More likely than not	Extremely likely
			Probability		

Table 2.2. Risk Matrix: percentage of flooded area and probability of the event.

- A. Average storm surge flooding for a 20-year event using RCP4.5 during the period (2041-2070)
- B. Average storm surge flooding for a 50-years event using RCP4.5 during the period (2041-2070)
- G. Average storm surge flooding for a 20-years event using RCP8.5 during the period (2071-2100)
- H. Average storm surge flooding for a 50-years event using RCP8.5 during the period (2071-2100)

This highlights a key limitation of traditional risk-based planning approaches: low probability does not justify inaction when consequences are catastrophic.

For Lemvig, this implies that adaptation measures should not be justified solely by probability, but by the need to ensure continuity, safety, and long-term habitability of the city.

Recommendations 3

In the following section, different recommendations for the problems are presented.

Considering the differences observed between the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios, a RCP4.5 scenario should be used for the period 2041-2070 while a RCP8.5 scenario would be best suited for longer-term planning, for the period 2071-2100. Either way, depending on how the climate evolves, the scenarios should be adapted again properly. The proposed recommendations should be understood as layers of adaptation, rather than mutually exclusive solutions, combining short-term protection with long-term resilience.

3.1 Solution for the lake

As shown in the analysis, the lake area may need some protection for extreme rain events, even if the risks are not nearly as great as storm events and sea-level rise. A solution for a 100mm/day rain event could be a 4cm tall wall for the Northern part of the lake (for the whole 2020-2100 period), and a 5.5cm tall wall for the Southern part of the lake (for the same period). The location of the walls is shown in figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1. Possible wall location to protect from the flood [SCALGO live, 2020]

3.2 The case of Skagen as a basis

Not only Lemvig but also other coastal regions are threatened by the rising sea-level. Skagen is also facing similar threats as Lemvig and in order to create a sustainable, but still attractive harbour front, the port of Skagen was expanded offshore [Port of Skagen, n.d.].

Based on this framework, a new approach tackling the issues in Lemvig is proposed in the following. Lemvig could also expand the harbour offshore and at the same time, incline the height towards the sea. This solution will take a certain amount of the sea area. However, making the harbour higher than the existing harbour front could help preventing future flooding. Furthermore, a wall can still be built at the end of the new harbour front. Taken these two measures into account, a larger sea-level rise can be accommodated without losing the attractiveness of the harbour front.

3.3 Adjustable/Flexible Flood Barriers

Another approach could be to use a similar system as the MOSE (MODulo Sperimentale Elettromeccanico, which is roughly translated to Electromechanic Experimental Module) system in Venice. More specifically, huge mobile gates could stop the floods from coming inside the city. Yet, the MOSE project costed more than 5 billion euros [ABC News, 2020], which is more expensive than the cost of Lemvig's wall (as stated in the introduction, this wall costed 18 million DKK [Broch, 2020]). Furthermore, the MOSE system is criticized by some environmentalists that emphasize possible environmental impacts of the project on local ecology, unforeseen consequences, and limitations [ABC News, 2020].

Figure 3.2. MOSE system [MOSE Venezia, 2020]

Another flood gate project could be inspired by Saint Petersburg Dam. This project has also downsides to it, such as risk of more polluted, stagnant water, and may end up being only permanent barriers that could not be opened anymore without causing a flood taking into account future sea-level rise [The Moscow Times, 2019].

Figure 3.3. Saint Petersburg Dam [The Moscow Times, 2019]

3.4 Sustainable Houses

Another approach is the adaptation towards sustainable houses, using flood protection barriers and drainage, respectively pumping systems. Besides this, the construction of new houses, which are in line with the sea-level rise, can help to live with the water, rather than keeping it out [Ngo et al., 2020]. As shown in Figure 3.4, the United Kingdom already built the so-called 'Amphibious houses' that are able to float during a flood period [Ngo et al., 2020].

Figure 3.4. Amphibious Houses [Ngo et al., 2020]

Next to the amphibious houses, the Netherlands built floating houses, that are completely water based. However, if the houses are located further away from the sea and only at risk due to storm surges, temporarily

solutions such as 'saving space for the water' could be used [Ngo et al., 2020]. This is illustrated in Figure 3.5.

Figure 3.5. Room for the Water [Ngo et al., 2020]

A semi-basement was constructed in order to store water in case of flooding. Combining it with artificial drainage may even increase the amount of water. Furthermore, floor elevation and floating floors have been proposed [Ngo et al., 2020].

Discussion 4

The city of Lemvig will face increasing challenges in the coming decades due to climate change, particularly as a result of sea-level rise, stronger storm surges, and more intense precipitation events. Given its close proximity to the sea, both the harbour and the urban core of Lemvig are exposed to significant flooding risks. Additionally, the lake constitutes a secondary risk area, especially during heavy rainfall events that may lead to flooding of the surrounding low-lying areas.

Under both RCP_{4.5} and RCP_{8.5} scenarios, the harbour front and parts of the city are projected to be flooded. Such events could result in damage to buildings, including residential areas, shops, and restaurants, and disrupt critical urban functions. This clearly highlights the necessity of adaptation measures alongside mitigation efforts. Planning and designing infrastructure for an uncertain climatic future therefore becomes essential. As discussed previously, the RCP_{4.5} scenario is considered appropriate for the period 2041–2070, with a re-evaluation required by mid-century, at which point the RCP_{8.5} scenario may become more relevant for the 2071–2100 period.

Given the inherent uncertainty associated with future climate trajectories, scalable and flexible adaptation measures should be prioritised. Such measures allow the city to respond progressively to changing conditions without committing prematurely to irreversible interventions.

The proposed intervention at the lake aims to minimise flooding of the surrounding areas during intense precipitation events. This solution has the advantage of being relatively easy to scale, for example by increasing the height of the retaining wall if required. However, it should be noted that this measure only addresses pluvial flooding and would not mitigate flooding caused by sea-level rise or storm surges, where water would directly enter the city from the sea.

An expansion of the harbour front, with or without the integration of flood gates, represents a more robust but also more complex solution. Such an intervention would require significant financial investment and major structural modifications. Moreover, the construction phase itself may raise sustainability concerns, including temporary pollution from machinery and potential impacts on the local ecosystem. In addition, these solutions are not easily scalable once implemented, as any future upgrades would demand substantial additional resources. Nevertheless, this approach offers a higher degree of certainty in terms of protection against extreme coastal flooding.

The use of flexible barriers would require not only advanced technology but also costly interventions at multiple locations throughout the city. These measures could also introduce challenges for the local ecosystem. On the other hand, when properly implemented, flexible barriers may provide faster and safer responses during extreme events, where reaction time is critical.

The creation of floodable areas presents an alternative strategy for a city that does not wish to retreat from

vulnerable zones. In this context, the transformation of the lowest parts of the valley into public spaces that can safely accommodate flooding should be carefully evaluated. Such an approach must consider infrastructure costs, land value, and the associated social and cultural heritage impacts.

Taking into account the analysed scenarios and the proposed recommendations, a promising approach that warrants further exploration is the expansion of the harbour front as a multifunctional structure. Rather than acting solely as a defensive wall, this intervention could create a secure, liveable, and attractive urban space. While it should be designed to accommodate more severe future scenarios, priority should be given to resilient developments, including sustainable housing typologies capable of tolerating occasional flooding. This strategy would allow the inhabitants of Lemvig to continue living in the valley while reducing reliance on high and visually intrusive flood walls.

From a long-term planning perspective, the findings of this assessment suggest a broader shift in sustainability thinking. The primary focus should move away from attempting to exclude water entirely and instead towards learning to live with it. In this sense, climate adaptation is not a failure of prevention, but a necessary and proactive strategy to enhance urban resilience in the face of unavoidable climate impacts.

This research builds on a climate risk assessment developed as part of a collaborative academic project. The discussion presented here synthesises and reflects on the outcomes of that collective work within the broader academic discourse on sustainability, planning, and climate adaptation policies.

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Appendix A

A.1 Map of certain constructions flooded by the sea level rise in the inner city

Figure A.1. RCP 8.5 scenario sea-level rise for 50-year event storm surge. Red line represents the road Enghavevej (taken from SCALGO)

Figure A.2. Map of abilities of the inner city of Lemvig (taken from google maps)